

Comparative Study of Ultrasound Guided Fascia Iliaca Compartment Block versus Pericapsular Nerve Group Block to Facilitate Positioning For Spinal Anaesthesia and Postoperative Analgesia in Hip Fracture Surgeries

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Abstract:

Background: Orthopaedic hip fractures are the predominant condition among aged people. An optimal preoperative pain management that reduces the use of opioids and mitigates their negative consequences is crucial in this specific group.

Aim and Objectives: The purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of Ultrasound guided Fascia Iliaca Compartment block (FICB) compared to Pericapsular nerve group (PENG) block in enabling the positioning for spinal anaesthesia and post-operative analgesia during surgeries for hip fracture.

Material and Methods: Following the approval of institutional ethical committee, a prospective interventional study was conducted on 46 patients aged 18-80 years, of either gender, who were classified as ASA class I, II, and III. These patients were randomly selected to receive either an Ultrasound guided PENG block (Group A, n=23) or a FICB block (Group B, n=23) using 40ml of 0.2% Ropivacaine. Prior to and after 30 minutes of the block, as well as while placing the patient for spinal anaesthesia, the blinded observer evaluated Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) scores at rest, with passive leg raise to 15°. The duration of postoperative pain relief and the level of patient acceptability were also documented. An analysis of the data was conducted using SPSS version 20. Statistical analysis was conducted on continuous and categorical data using the suitable statistical approach. A significance level of $P \geq 0.05$ was used to determine statistical significance.

Result: Subjected to a passive leg raise to 15° when at rest, the VAS scores in the PENG and FICB groups showed a substantial reduction ($P < 0.001$). Following 30 minutes of administering the PENG block, the VAS scores at rest and passive leg raise were 0.4 ± 0.5 and 1.01 ± 0.7 , respectively. In contrast, the VAS scores at rest and passive leg raise with the fascia iliaca block were 1.1 ± 0.7 and 1.6 ± 0.8 , respectively, with statistically significant p-values of 0.001 and 0.022, respectively. The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) score 30 minutes after the block during placement was 2.1 ± 0.6 in the FICB group and 1.6 ± 0.7 in the PENG group ($P = 0.008$). A substantial difference was seen in the duration of analgesia between the PENG group (487.73 ± 38.61 minutes) and the FICB group (431.74 ± 25.16 minutes) ($P < 0.001$). Requirement for postoperative opioid rescue analgesia was much lower ($P = 0.011$) in the PENG group compared to the FICB group. Superior patient acceptability was noted in the PENG group ($P = 0.028$).

Conclusion: The effectiveness of PENG block in delivering analgesia before positioning the patients awaiting hip surgery under spinal anaesthesia surpasses that of fascia iliaca block. However, both the blocks successfully maintained haemodynamic stability without any significant adverse consequences.

Keywords: Hip fractures; Fascia iliaca block; VAS scores; Pericapsular nerve group block.

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Introduction

The hip fracture is a prevalent orthopedic disorder among the elderly population, characterised by intense pain that hinders the ability to position the patient for spinal anaesthesia. [1] Given the presence of concurrent medical conditions in older

people, regional anaesthesia is the preferable choice over general anaesthesia. [2] Regional anaesthesia in surgeries for fractured hip is associated with reduced mortality and morbidity compared to general anaesthesia. [3] Positioning

the patient for subarachnoid block is very agonizing, necessitates increased dosages of sedatives and narcotics, and is undesirable in elderly patients. [4] Pain treatment should start promptly after the fracture to enable thorough testing, radiographic examinations, and transportation. [5]

Prescription opioids were the most often used therapy for orthopedic pain. Nevertheless, the use of opioids in elderly persons has been associated with a multitude of undesirable outcomes, including low blood pressure, confusion, extended hospital stay, respiratory depression, and negative consequences after discharge such as addiction or dependency. [6] Regional nerve blocks can effectively control hip fracture pain by delivering rapid onset, site-specific analgesia that is particularly effective compared to standard systemic analgesia alone. Furthermore, there is evidence to support the claims that nerve blocks minimize hospital stays and lower rates of morbidity, mortality, and delirium. [7] Regional analgesia provides superior pain relief and fewer adverse effects compared to opioids, making it safer to use. In addition to its application in operating theatres, regional analgesia may also be employed in emergency rooms to facilitate patient assessment, transfer, and radiological measurements. [8] The fascia iliaca compartment block (FICB) is a routine local analgesic technique employed by anesthesiologists to block the obturator, femoral, and lateral cutaneous nerves. It involves injecting anaesthetic between the fascia iliaca and the psoas muscle. [9] Research suggests that the auxiliary obturator nerve is unaffected by blockages, as these blocks only offer little pain relief.

The Pericapsular Nerve Group (PENG) block is a novel regional anaesthesia technique that specifically targets the obturator nerve, the auxiliary obturator nerve (if present), and the articular branches of the femoral nerve that supply sensation to the anterior capsule of the hip. This block is administered with a single injection. In a tertiary academic hospital, the present study aims to assess the effectiveness and safety of Ultrasound guided Pericapsular nerve group block for positioning during spinal anaesthesia and postoperative analgesia for hip fracture surgeries, compared to Ultrasound guided Fascia Iliaca compartment block.

Aim and Objectives:

The aim of present study is to compare the effect of Ultrasound guided Fascia Iliaca Compartment block versus Pericapsular nerve group block to facilitate the positioning for spinal anaesthesia and post-operative analgesia in hip fracture surgeries.

Primary Objectives: Comparison of pain scores using VAS during positioning of the patient for spinal anaesthesia after administration of block.

Secondary Objectives: Assessment of total duration of complete effective analgesia and postoperative need of rescue analgesia as well as any associated notable side effects.

Material and Methods

The study was done as a hospital based prospective interventional study at the Department of Anaesthesiology, Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Research Centre, located in Tumkur, Karnataka, India. Patients aged 18-80 years, scheduled for elective hip fracture surgeries, were recruited for the research after obtaining clearance from the institutional ethics committee (Ref No.: (SSMC/MED/IEC-132/July-2022) and informed consent from the patients.

A total of 46 individuals were chosen for hip surgery, following the acquisition of written informed consent. Inclusion criteria were as follows: age range between 18 and 80 years, physical status Class I, II, and III according to the "American Society of Anaesthesiologists" (ASA), and body mass index below 29.9 kg.m⁻². The exclusion criteria for this study were infection at the injection site, allergy to local anaesthetics, prolonged opioid use for analgesic treatment or concurrent use of other analgesics up to 8 hours before nerve block, coagulopathy, and presence of an inguinal hernia on the same side as hip pathology.

The sample size calculation was done by using convenient sampling method with the help of the following formula, $n = \{(1-\alpha/2) + (1-\beta)\} 2[p_1(1-p_1) + p_2(1-p_2)] / d^2$

The minimum sample size required was 21 in each group (total = 42). Considering non-response rate of 10%, the total sample size required was 46.

Upon arrival in the operating room, participants were at random assigned to receive either an ultrasound-guided PENG block (n = 23) or FICB (n = 23) using a computer-generated random number sequence and a closed opaque envelope technique. A non-participating research colleague created the randomization list and opaque envelopes for the study. Upon transferring the patients to the operation room, accurate measurements of all essential vital parameters were taken. Prior to the delivery of the block, the patient provided an explanation of the visual analogue score (VAS). Preoperative pain was evaluated both at rest and while the leg was raised to 15° passively. In the passive leg raise technique, the afflicted limb of a patient lying on their back was gently elevated to an angle of around 15°, with a little bending of the

hip and knee in extension. Initially, this VAS was regarded as a baseline score.

Group A [Ultrasound guided PENG block]: received Ropivacaine 0.2% 40ml.

Group B [ultrasound guided Fascia Iliaca Block]: received Ropivacaine 0.2% 40ml.

Methodology:

For PENG block, after skin disinfection and local infiltration, a low-frequency (2–5 MHz) curvilinear ultrasound probe was placed parallel at the level of the anterior superior iliac spine. The iliopubic bulge of the iliopsoas muscle, femoral artery, and pectineus muscle was observed by rotating the probe counter clockwise 45 degrees. By the in-plane method, the needle was inserted from lateral to the medial until the tip placed in the facial muscle between the anterior tendon and the superior pubis ramus. After negative aspiration, ropivacaine 0.2% was injected at a rate of 3 mg/kg (maximum of 40 ml).

For FICB, after skin disinfection and local infiltration, cutaneous anaesthesia, a high-frequency linear transducer (10–25 MHz) ultrasound device (S-Nerve Sonosite) was placed 2 cm inferomedial to the ASIS in sagittal plane where sartorius, internal oblique, iliopsoas muscles and fascia Iliaca are identified. By rotating the probe, the Bowtie sign formed by above structures is identified then an 80MM 22G Quincke spinal needle is advanced using in-plane approach till needle tip is placed between the iliac Fascia and the iliopsoas muscle. Using hydro-dissection method the correct plane is identified and then- ropivacaine 0.2% was injected at a rate of 3 mg/kg (maximum of 40 ml) after negative aspiration.

Patients had continuous monitoring for systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), heart rate, pulse oximetry, continuous electrocardiogram (ECG), and local anaesthetic

toxicity symptoms for 30 minutes following the block. A 30-minute post-blocks VAS score was re-evaluated both at rest and with passive leg elevation to 15°. A separate anesthesiologist, who was unaware of the management of the regional block, conducted each of the observations.

Under aseptic conditions, a 25-gauge Quincke's spinal needle was used to deliver 2.5-3 mL of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine while the patient was seated. The anaesthetist delivering the spinal anaesthesia evaluated the quality of patient positioning on a scale of 0 to 3 (0=unacceptable, 1=acceptable, 2=desirable, 3=optimal). Patient acceptance of the posture was also noted (yes or no).

The duration of analgesia was determined from the moment the block was administered until the VAS score reached ≥ 4 .

VAS scores were recorded at 0, 2hr, 6hr, 8hr, 10hr, 12hr and 24hrs along with vital parameters.

Patients with VAS more than 4 received Inj. Tramadol IV 1mg/kg as rescue analgesic in postoperative period. The total tramadol use throughout the first 24 hours was recorded. Complications if any were documented and appropriately treated.

Statistical Analysis: The data was entered in Excel spread sheet. Descriptive statistical analysis was been carried out. Quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation and qualitative variables was presented as frequency and percentages. The association between categorical variables was analyzed by applying Chi-square test. The data will be analyzed by using SPSS software (version 20).

Results

Comparable demographic variables, ASA grades, surgical procedures, and duration of surgery were observed in both groups. [Table 1]

Table 1: Demographic variables

Variables	Group A (PENG block)	Group B (FICB block)	P-value
Mean age (years)	52.20±9.6	52.70±11.8	0.871 (NS)
Gender	Male	15	0.546 (NS)
	Female	08	
ASA grade	I	09	0.783 (NS)
	II	12	
	III	02	

NS- Non Significant

Comparable mean VAS scores were observed in both groups during rest and passive leg raise prior to the block ($P = 0.480$ and 0.677 , respectively). Significantly decreased VAS scores were seen 30 minutes after the block in both groups, both at rest

as well as with movement ($P < 0.001$ and 0.022 , respectively). An analysis of VAS ratings 30 minutes following nerve block while poisoning revealed a statistically significant difference ($P=0.008$). [Table 2]

Table 2: Comparison of VAS scores among groups

Groups	Pre-block VAS (Mean±SD)		Post-block VAS (Mean±SD)			Mean reduction in pain	
	Rest	Passive limb elevation	Rest	Passive limb elevation	During positioning	Rest	Passive limb elevation
Group A (PENG block) (n=23)	6.30±0.7	7.70±0.7	0.40±0.5	1.01±0.7	1.60±0.7	5.91±0.9	6.80±1.1
Group B (FICB block) (n=23)	6.50±0.5	7.80±0.7	1.10±0.7	1.6±0.8	2.10±0.6	5.30±0.8	6.20±0.7
P-value	0.480 (NS)	0.677 (NS)	<0.001 (S)	0.022 (S)	0.008 (S)	0.027 (S)	0.016 (S)

NS- Not Significant ($p>0.05$), S- Significant ($p<0.05$)

There was no statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of mean heart rate (HR), Mean arterial pressure (MAP) and mean SPO₂ ($P>0.05$). We did not encounter any block-related complications. Quality of patient positioning and patient acceptance for the block were found to be statistically significant among both the groups. [Table 3]

Table 3: Quality of patient positioning and patient acceptance for the block

Parameters	Group A (PENG block)	Group B (FICB block)	P-value
Quality of patient positioning	2.57±0.5	2.13±0.3	0.001 (S)
Patient acceptance for the block (Yes/No)	19/04	12/11	0.028 (S)

S- Significant ($p<0.05$)

The duration of analgesia in PENG group; 487.73 ± 38.61 minutes, was significantly longer than that of FICB group; 431.74 ± 25.16 minutes, ($P<0.001$). Need of postoperative opioid rescue analgesia was significantly lesser ($P=0.011$) in PENG group when compared to FICB group. [Table 4]

Table 4: Duration of post-operative analgesia and need of opioid rescue analgesia

Parameters	Group A (PENG block)	Group B (FICB block)	P-value
Duration of post-operative analgesia	487.73±38.61	431.74±25.16	<0.001 (S)
Total analgesic required in 1st 24hrs (No. of doses)	2.2 ± 0.5	2.6 ± 0.5	0.011(S)

S- Significant ($p<0.05$)

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that both PENG and fascia iliaca blocks significantly reduced VAS ratings both at rest and during passive leg raise measurements. Nevertheless, the PENG block demonstrated superior pain alleviation compared to FICB while preparing patients for spinal anaesthesia, as seen by decreased VAS values during passive leg raise.

Achieving correct placement is essential for the successful execution of surgical anaesthesia in patients with hip fractures, which need sufficient pain relief. Given the majority of patients are older and have many health conditions, peripheral nerve blocks are the preferable method for alleviating pain and preventing the widespread use of opioids. FICB and PENG blocks are often employed analgesic blocks applied during spinal positioning procedures.

The objective of this study is to evaluate the analgesic efficacy of the FICB and PENG block in achieving appropriate positioning for spinal

anaesthesia. While both the PENG block and FICB offer effective pain relief for patient positioning, there is a scarcity of case series and reports in the existing literature available. A fascia iliaca block is a compound block procedure that affects the femoral nerve, obturator nerve, and lateral femoral cutaneous nerve. However, it is often seen that the obturator nerve is spared with this block. Shariat et al. [11] found no significant difference in postoperative pain scores or 24-hour opioid use between the FICB with 0.5% ropivacaine and the sham block with 0.9% normal saline in THA treatment patients. The research project undertaken by Kacha et al. [12] was a randomized, controlled, double-blind prospective study included 100 patients who were scheduled to have hip or proximal femoral surgery. Their findings indicated a significant decrease in VAS scores while using FICB with 30 mL of 0.25% ropivacaine, as compared to SHAM block with 30 mL of normal saline. Our study also revealed a notable decrease in pain scores following frontal intercostal block (FICB).

Based on cadaveric studies, the PENG block is a novel regional analgesic block that specifically targets the articular branches leading to the anterior area of the hip joint with a single injection. The present investigation provides evidence of the involvement of the auxiliary obturator nerve in the anterior hip joint. Giron Arango et al. [10] performed a case study of five participants who had suffered hip fractures. The PENG block was administered to all five patients who exhibited a decrease in pain levels, both at rest and during passive leg raise. The highest reported VAS score from the PENG block was 2. A case series study conducted by Sahoo et al. [13] comprised nine patients who had been slated for surgery to repair a hip fracture. Both the VAS scores at rest as well as during passive leg raise had been markedly decreased in all 9 patients who had PENG block. The findings of our investigation were likewise consistent; there was a significant decrease in VAS scores following the administration of the PENG block.

Few researches have conducted a comparison between FICB and PENG block. According to Senthil et al., [14] PENG block demonstrated superior postoperative analgesic effectiveness in comparison to FICB. A considerably longer initial time of analgesic need after surgery was seen with the PENG block compared to the FICB ($P = 0.007$). In comparison to the FICB group, the total amount of morphine required in the PENG block appeared significantly lower ($P = 0.008$). Senthil et al., [14] randomly assigned forty patients with hip fracture to undergo either PENG or FICB blocks. They studied the duration of postoperative analgesia and dynamic pain levels and found no significant difference between the two modalities. Their findings revealed a notable disparity in motor power between VAS and quadriceps, suggesting that sensory block and quadriceps motor sparing are more effective in PENG block compared to FICB.

Jadon et al. [15] conducted a study comparing suprainguinal FICB with PENG block for placement in 66 patients scheduled for surgery. Their findings indicated that the NRS score following a 30-minute block at rest with S-FICB was 4, while with PENG block, it was 3. The NRS score for passive leg raise using S-FICB was 5, but for PENG block it was 4. However, during the FICB procedure, a suprainguinal technique was applied.

In their controlled investigation, Bhattacharya et al. [16] examined a cohort of 50 patients who had fractured neck femur. Each arm of the trial included 25 participants who had a PENG block or FICB using 20 mL of 0.25% levobupivacaine. The author's conclusion is that both FICB and PENG blocks are about equally efficacious, with PENG

delivering pain relief more rapidly in patients with femur neck fractures. The results of our analysis indicate that the analgesic effectiveness of PENG block was superior to that of fascia iliaca block.

The study's strength lies in the implementation of double blinding to minimize chance bias. The present work additionally documented the haemodynamic response.

Limitation of study

This study has few limitations. First, the use of patient-controlled analgesia would have been better to get an idea of 24-hour opioids consumption than the request for demand analgesia. However, this was compensated by keeping patients in high-dependency units following surgery with adequate nursing support. Second, assessment of motor functions in the postoperative period would have given us an idea of whether PENG block is truly motor sparing. Another of the limitation of our study was assessment of VAS score which is subjective and can vary with the level of understanding between patient and anesthesiologists. Last, smaller sample size reduces the power of study.

Conclusion

PENG block is superior to fascia iliaca block in providing effective analgesia prior to positioning of patients posted for hip surgeries under spinal anaesthesia.

We recommend more widespread use of USG guided PENG block for perioperative analgesia in patients with hip fractures as it provides satisfactory analgesia and patient comfort. We also recommend further randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes are required to validate the efficacy and superiority of the PENG blocks over conventional techniques.

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